

Blueprint for national events on future colliders for early-career researchers

Context

The European Strategy for Particle Physics ([ESPP](#)) was last updated in 2019. The input of the early-career researcher (ECR) community ([arXiv:2002.02837](#)) was collected at a late stage in an ad-hoc manner. As a follow-up to the ESPP update, the European Committee for Future Colliders (ECFA) created the ECFA ECR panel with representatives from all ECFA Countries and CERN (see [webpage](#)). The next update of the ESPP is planned starting in 2025 and finishing in June 2026, which is important for the future of the field given the pending decision on the next world-leading collider.

In September 2023, the Future Colliders Working Group of the ECFA ECR panel organised the *Future Colliders for Early-Career Researchers* ([agenda](#)) taking place at CERN and online. The event aimed to inform ECRs on future colliders and to foster discussion on this important topic in the ECR community. Since many aspects related to future colliders, such as funding and career opportunities, are country-dependent, national follow-up events should be organised. One such event series has already taken place in the UK ([agenda](#)) and this document presents a blueprint for how such an event can be structured. The goal is to have one such event in every ECFA member country, with the possibility of joining forces between neighbouring countries (e.g. Nordic countries) to ease the load on the organisers.

Format

The national events should be half a day to a day, with strong in-person participation. Ideally, the event is scheduled to be adjacent to other particle physics meetings in the country (e.g. workshops, conferences, restricted ECFA country visits, etc.). The sessions should be convened by ECRs and feature as many ECRs as possible as speakers. Seniors of course are also welcome to the events and are crucial for many discussions e.g. on funding.

In the following, we list the sessions and topics that we think are necessary for a successful event. The event is structured into four sessions focusing on different aspects of future colliders.

Introduction session

This session is meant to introduce the need for future colliders to the ECR community. The first talk should be about the current landscape of HEP and the open questions. After this, the various future collider options are introduced and compared. This talk could be given by an accelerator physicist who can go through the challenges associated with the various proposals. Given that an ECFA-wide event on future colliders for ECRs took place in Sep. 2023, a short talk could be inserted to get some more input on what could be discussed during the event.

Institute session

In this session, the national institutes and labs present their current activities and their interest in future collider-related R&D. First a short overview of the past and current national HEP involvement should be presented. This look back in time can help to understand how the next step to future colliders can succeed in terms of the organisation of a national effort.

Next, the current involvement in future colliders (possibly also accelerator R&D, civil engineering studies, etc.) is discussed. This contribution can be extended if there is already a lot of work ongoing on future colliders.

Finally, each national institute or lab is shortly (max. 5 slides each) presenting their interest in future colliders.

People and money session

The *People and Money* session is the centrepiece of each national future colliders event. First, the connection to society should be stressed. Questions of sustainability for example need to be addressed. Overall, the national HEP community must find a way to communicate the benefits of a future collider both to researchers of other fields and to society to ensure that such a project is widely supported.

Next to this, the national funding structure should be presented by a senior researcher or funding agency representative as many ECRs might not be familiar with this. The example of LHC experiments funding can be used to discuss how future collider R&D may be financed in the future.

At the end of the People and Money session, a panel discussion is held discussing the next steps for national future collider R&D efforts. The guiding questions could be:

- What can we learn from past efforts at LHC or other large-scale science projects?
- How to make a career working on future colliders?
- National support for future collider R&D from funding agencies, universities and other stakeholders?
- How to “sell” future colliders to the national public?
- How to organise the national structure of future collider efforts? Next steps?

The event ends with conclusions by the meeting organisers.

Example agenda

In the following, an example agenda for a national event on future colliders for ECRs is shown, following the rough structure of the ECFA-wide event at CERN. Example talks given in the past on the proposed topics are linked.

Introduction session

09:00-09:10	Introduction to the event	Organisers
09:10-09:40	Current physics landscape and motivation for future collider. 20+10 min (example1 , example2)	Exp. or theo. particle physicist from country
09:40-10:20	Overview of future colliders options. 30+10 min (example1 , example2)	National accel. physicist or person already working on a FC
10:20-10:40	Summary of ECFA-wide event on future colliders (example1 , example2) and/or on status of ESPP and P5. 10+10 min	Organiser of ECFA-wide event or someone already engaged in future collider discussions
10:40-11:10	Break	
Institute session		
11:10-11:25	Past and current national HEP involvement of the country. 10+5 min.	Senior LHC physicist from the country
11:25-11:40	Current national involvement in future colliders. 10+5 min (example)	ECR working on future colliders from the country
11:40-12:40	National research interests related to future colliders (a couple of slides per institute, example)	One person per institute (if possible ECR)
12:40-13:40	Lunch break. Could include a poster session on future collider-related work	
Bonus session (country dependent)		
13:40-15:10	<p>Possible ideas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - View from different fields (within particle physics or even beyond, example) - Guided discussion on future colliders with the audience (example) - Continuation of institute session - Discussing possible fields of collaboration on future colliders in-between institutes - Survey on ECR opinion on future colliders 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Talks or panel discussion on sustainability (example) - Discussion on career opportunities and challenges in the country 	
15:10-15:40	Coffee break	
People and money session		
16:10-16:40	Impact on future colliders on society and sustainability. 20+10 min (example)	Someone leading outreach in the country or invested in sustainability in HEP
16:40-17:10	National funding structure and plans for future collider R&D. 20+10 min (example)	Senior national researcher or funding agency representative
17:10-18:00	<p>Future colliders panel discussion</p> <p>Panelists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (ECFA) ECR representatives - ECR working on future colliders - RECFA and/or chair of the national particle physics organisation - National accelerator physicist (if available) - Representative of the funding agency - View from a different country working on future colliders 	<p>Moderated by one ECR and one senior person</p> <p>Take input from the audience through previously submitted and/or live questions</p>
18:00-18:15	Conclusions and next steps	Organisers

The discussions on future colliders are crucial input to the next ESPP update

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